

Kinetics of the ascorbate depletion driven by transition metals and naphthoquinone under different fluid composition

A. Expósito¹, J. Maillo¹, M. Santibáñez² and I. Fernández-Olmo¹

¹Departamento de Ingenierías Química y Biomolecular,
Universidad de Cantabria, Santander, Spain

²Departamento de Enfermería, Universidad de Cantabria,
Santander, Spain

Keywords: kinetic, ascorbate, metals, artificial lysosomal fluid, chloride.

Associated conference topics: 4.6

andrea.exposito@unican.es

Ascorbic acid (AA) is one of the lung lining antioxidants used to quantify the particulate matter (PM) oxidative potential (OP). The most commonly used ascorbic acid assay quantifies PM OP following the ascorbate depletion rate using a UV/VIS spectrophotometer. The ascorbic acid oxidative potential (OP-AA) of PM is particularly sensitive to copper and iron in ambient aerosol. However, there is not clear consensus on which experimental factors should be applied (Pietrogrande *et al*, 2021). To understand the effects of experimental conditions on the OP-AA assay and to select suitable parameters, it is necessary to investigate the kinetics of AA oxidation in the presence of PM-bound pollutants known to catalyse this oxidation.

Earlier studies described the ascorbate (AH⁻) oxidation catalysed by metals (with excess of oxygen) by equation 1, e.g. first-order with respect to AH⁻ and the catalyst (Buettner, 1988):

$$\frac{d[AH^-]}{dt} = k_{cat} \cdot [catalyst] \cdot [AH^-] \quad (1)$$

However, different reaction orders of ascorbate and catalysts were also reported (Fábián and Csordás, 2003). Besides, some studies investigated the effect of the reaction conditions, such as pH, temperature, and chloride concentration, on the catalytic constant (k_{cat}). These factors in the measurement of PM OP-AA are conditioned by the fluid used. The most widely used fluid is neutral phosphate buffer, although different buffer compositions were applied. Besides, simulated lung fluids, such as Artificial Lysosomal Fluid (ALF, pH 4.5) and Gamble's solutions (pH 7.4), have been recently used in OP assays.

The aim of this work is to develop kinetic models of ascorbate oxidation driven by metals and quinones in synthetic fluids with different pH and composition to increase the knowledge regarding the effect of such parameters on the rate of the ascorbate oxidation. With this aim, the ascorbate depletion in the presence of three individual metal salts (FeCl₃, FeCl₂, CuSO₄) and 1,4-naphthoquinone (1,4-NQ) in three different fluids across a range of environmentally relevant concentrations was measured. Two neutral buffers with different sodium chloride concentration were investigated: phosphate buffer saline (PBS1x, 0.01M phosphate, 0.1 M NaCl) and

phosphate buffer (PB, 0.05M phosphate). Besides, an acidic simulated lung fluid, ALF, was studied. This fluid is of particular interest due to its acidic pH and its complex composition. The ascorbate depletion curves were obtained measuring the absorbance ($\lambda=265$ nm) of each solution with time (up to 120 minutes) using a microplate reader (Thermo Multiskan Skyhigh). Reaction orders and kinetic constants were calculated minimizing the RMSE between modelled and observed concentrations.

The kinetic models developed indicate that the reaction order of ascorbate varied as a function of the fluid and the pure compound used in the reaction. For example, the reaction order of ascorbate in the presence of Cu was 0 in PBS1x, but ranged from 0.5 to 1 when Cu, Fe or 1,4-NQ were dissolved in PB. In addition, the reaction order of individual catalytic compounds in each fluid was compared, obtaining in most cases reaction orders between 0.5 and 1.

In brief, the kinetics of ascorbate oxidation driven by each pure compound differed depending on the pH and the fluid composition. So, experimental factors, such as the initial ascorbate concentration (to be fixed in the assay) and the concentrations of PM compounds (which will vary in PM samples), could affect the OP-AA responses differently depending on the applied fluid. Consequently, significant differences in OP-AA values and their correlations with PM pollutants can be expected when real PM samples are collected.

In view of these results, the pH and the composition of fluids should be considered to set suitable OP-AA protocols and to assure comparable results.

This work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (Project PID2020-428 114787RB-I00).

Buettner, G.R. (1988) *J. Biochem. Biophys. Methods* **16(1)**, 27-40.

Fábián, I. and Csordás, C. (2003) *Advan. in Inorganic Chemist.* **54(41)**, 395-461.

Pietrogrande, M.C. *et al* (2021) *Environ. Science and Pollution Res.* **28**, 29551-29563.